

Preparation of Acetoxyacetylisocoumarins

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Experiments on the introduction of acetoxyacetyl groups at the 3 and 4 positions of isocoumarins are described.

In experiments devised towards the synthesis of oosponol (I)¹ or its acetate (II), containing COCH₂OH and COCH₂OAc groups respectively, we had two synthetic methods in view : (i) conversion of diazoacetyl group into COCH₂OH and COCH₂OAc by varying the acid, (ii) the nucleophilic displacement of the corresponding α -haloketone with acetoxy group. The first method proved complicated because of the conjugate addition of diazomethane with the double bond although Mori *et al.*² were able to synthesise and separate oosponol diacetate in 0.02% yield. The reason of the low yield is obvious. The second route proved more effective. Thus isocoumarin-4-carboxylic acid (III)³ was converted into 4-acetyl-isocoumarin (IV) and thence to 4-bromoacetylisocoumarin (V) which reacted with sodium acetate in acetic acid to give 4-(ω -acetoxyacetyl)-isocoumarin (VI). The compounds by the second route have now been reported by Kokubo *et al.*⁴ in patent literature. Since our physical data are in complete agreement with his, the preparation of these compounds have not been described in experimental. However, it may be mentioned that hydrolysis of the 4-(ω -acetoxyacetyl)isocoumarin (VI) with 10% H₂SO₄ gave a compound m.p. 290°, showing a molecular ion peak at m/e, 372. The compound showed the presence of lactone carbonyl (i.r. absorption at 1738 cm⁻¹) and an absence of hydroxyl group. The molecular weight and elemental analysis indicate that the compound may be formed from two molecules of 4-(ω -hydroxyacetyl) isocoumarin *minus* two molecules of water (2 × 204 - 2 × 18 = 372) and further investigation is necessary for the determination of its structure.

- I, R₁ = OH, R₂ = H, R₃ = COCH₂OH
 II, R₁ = OH, R₂ = H, R₃ = COCH₂OAc
 III, R₁ = R₂ = H, R₃ = COOH
 IV, R₁ = R₂ = H, R₃ = COCH₃
 V, R₁ = R₂ = H, R₃ = COCH₂Br
 VI, R₁ = R₂ = H, R₃ = COCH₂OAc

- VII, R₁ = COOH
 VIII, R₁ = COCH₃
 IX, R₁ = COCH₂Br
 X, R₁ = COCH₂OAc

(0.2 g.) for 5 hrs on water bath. Water was then added and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water and dried (MgSO_4). On evaporation of the solvent, 6,7-dimethoxy-4-(ω -acetoxyacetyl)isocoumarin (0.15 g.) immediately separated, which on crystallisation from acetic acid afforded cream coloured granules, m.p. 173° (Found : C, 58.6; H, 5.0. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_7$ requires : C, 58.8; H, 4.6%).

IR Spectrum : Absorption at 1739 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl), 1728 cm^{-1} (acetate carbonyl), 1698 cm^{-1} (carbonyl) and 1240 cm^{-1} (O-CO stretching of acetate).

3-Diazoacetylisocoumarin (XI, R = COCHN₂) : An ethereal suspension of the acid chloride prepared from isocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid⁷ (1.2 g.) was added to dry ethereal diazomethane prepared from nitrosomethylurea (9.0 g.) and kept overnight in a refrigerator. Next day, ether was removed under reduced pressure and the diazoketone (XI, R = COCHN₂) (1.0 g.) so obtained was crystallised from benzene to give straw yellow cubic crystals, m.p. 176° - 77° (decomp.) (Found : N, 12.7. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ requires : N, 13.0%).

3-(ω -Hydroxyacetyl) isocoumarin (XI, R = COCH₂OH) : The diazoketone (XI, R = COCHN₂) (0.5 g.) in dioxan (5 ml.) was warmed on water bath with 2N H_2SO_4 (3 ml.) until the evolution of nitrogen ceased (about 2.5 hrs). It was extracted with ether, the extract washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and water and finally dried (MgSO_4). Evaporation of the solvent afforded 3-(ω -hydroxyacetyl)isocoumarin (0.2 g.) which crystallised from benzene as light yellow crystals, m.p. 163° - 64° (Found : C, 65.0; H, 4.1. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 64.7; H, 3.9%).

IR Spectrum : Absorptions at 1735 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl) and 1710 cm^{-1} (carbonyl).

3-(ω -Acetoxyacetyl)isocoumarin (XI, R = COCH₂OAc) : The diazoketone (XI, R = COCHN₂) (0.5 g.) in acetic acid (3 ml.) was warmed on water bath until the evolution of nitrogen ceased. The mixture was extracted with ether, the extract washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and water and dried (MgSO_4). Evaporation of the solvent gave 3-(ω -acetoxyacetyl)isocoumarin (0.2 g.) which crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in light yellow plates, m.p. 175° - 76° (Found : C, 63.1; H, 4.3. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5$ requires : C, 63.4; H, 4.0%).

IR Spectrum : Absorptions at 1750 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl), 1740 cm^{-1} (acetate carbonyl), 1715 cm^{-1} (carbonyl) and 1240 cm^{-1} (O-CO stretching of acetate).

Acetylation of 3-(ω -Hydroxyacetyl)isocoumarin : 3-(ω -Hydroxyacetyl)isocoumarin (0.1 g.) was treated with acetyl chloride (0.1 ml.) and pyridine (2 drops) and warmed on water bath for 20 mins. It was cooled, diluted with water and extracted with ether. The extract was washed with water and dried (MgSO_4). Removal of the solvent yielded 3-(ω -acetoxyacetyl)isocoumarin, m.p. and mixed m.p. 175° , giving identical i.r. spectrum with that of the authentic acetate (XI, R = COCH₂OAc).

Hydrolysis of 3-(ω -Acetoxyacetyl)isocoumarin : 3-(ω -Acetoxyacetyl)isocoumarin (0.1 g.) was refluxed with 10% H_2SO_4 (2 ml.) for 3 hrs. The cooled solution was extracted with chloroform, the extract washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water and finally dried (MgSO_4). Evaporation of the solvent yielded a compound, which was found to be identical (i.r. spectrum and mixed m.p.) with 3-(ω -hydroxyacetyl) isocoumarin.

3-Acetylisocoumarin (XI, R = COCH₃) : Diethyl ethoxymagnesiummalonate was prepared from magnesium (0.14 g.), dry alcohol (0.63 ml.), carbon tetrachloride (0.02 ml.), diethyl malonate (0.9 ml.) and dry ether (3 ml.) in the same way as described for the preparation of (VIII). To this mixture, an ethereal solution of the acid chloride prepared from isocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid (0.6 g.) was added with stirring and the mixture refluxed for 2 hrs when the magnesium complex separated as a jelly. The reaction mixture was decomposed with dilute sulphuric acid and extracted with ether. After removal of the solvent, the residual oil was refluxed with a mixture of acetic acid (1.2 ml.), sulphuric acid (0.1 ml.) and water (0.7 ml.) for 4.5 hrs and then cooled. The solid (0.3 g.) which separated was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from alcohol as cream coloured needles, m.p. 139°–40° (Found : C, 70.5; H, 4.5. C₁₁H₈O₃ requires : C, 70.2; H, 4.2%).

IR Spectrum : Absorptions at 1725 cm⁻¹ (lactone carbonyl) and 1680 cm⁻¹ (carbonyl).

NMR Spectrum : It shows proton signals at τ 7.42 (singlet, 3H, COCH₃) and the vinyl proton has merged into aromatic region which is spread between τ 1.6 and 2.75, due to the conjugated carbonyl group at 3 position.

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative was prepared which crystallised from acetic acid as yellow needles, m.p. 281° (Found : N, 15.3. C₁₇H₁₂O₆N₄ requires : N, 15.2%).

3-(ω -Bromoacetyl)isocoumarin (XI, R = COCH₂Br) : To a solution of 3-acetylisocoumarin (0.5 g.) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml.) was added a solution of bromine (0.425 g.) in acetic acid (4 ml.) and the mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature till it turned straw yellow in colour. The mixture was then powdered into crushed ice when solid (0.4g.) separated which crystallised from alcohol as cream coloured rods, m.p. 156°–57° (Found : C, 49.3; H, 2.5. C₁₁H₇O₃Br requires : C, 49.4; H, 2.6%).

IR Spectrum : Absorptions at 1725 cm⁻¹ (lactone carbonyl) and 1710 cm⁻¹ (carbonyl).

3-(ω -Acetoxyacetyl)isocoumarin (XI, R = COCH₂OAc) : To a solution of the above bromoketone (0.5 g.) in acetic acid (2 ml.) fused potassium acetate (0.3 g.) was added and heated on water bath for 3 hrs. Water was then added to it, extracted with ether, the extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water and finally dried (MgSO₄). Evaporation of the solvent afforded 3-(ω -acetoxyacetyl)isocoumarin (0.4 g.) which crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in light yellow plates, m.p. 175°–76°, identical (i.r. spectrum and mixed m.p.) with the authentic specimen previously prepared. (Found : C, 63.3; H, 4.4. C₁₃H₁₀O₅ requires : C, 63.4; H, 4.1%).

NMR Spectrum : It consists of proton signals at τ 7.75 (singlet, 3H, -OCOCH₃), τ 4.7 (singlet, 2H, CH₂OAc) and vinyl proton has merged into aromatic region which is spread between τ 1.15 and 2.65.

Isocoumarin-3-acetic acid (XI, R = CH₂COOH) : The diazoketone (XI, R = COCHN₂) (1.0 g.) in dry methanol (20 ml.) was heated on water bath; to it was added a small amount of slurry of silver oxide (0.2 g.) in dry methanol (15 ml.) and stirred. As soon as the evolution of nitrogen subsided, more of silver oxide was introduced and this process was continued until all the slurry had been added. The mixture was then refluxed for 15 hrs on water bath. Within this period about 0.8 g. of silver oxide was added in instalments. Then the

mixture was heated with charcoal, filtered and solvent evaporated to give methyl isocoumarin-3-acetate (0.4 g.) which crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in light yellow needles, m.p. 115°-17° (Found : C, 65.8; H, 4.5. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires : C, 66.0; H, 4.5%).

IR Spectrum : Absorptions at 1750 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl) and 1725 cm^{-1} (ester carbonyl).

The above ester dissolved in a mixture of acetic acid (2 ml.) and hydrochloric acid (1 ml.) was refluxed for 4 hrs. Acetic acid was removed under reduced pressure and the residue taken up in ether. The ethereal solution was extracted with sodium bicarbonate solution. The bicarbonate extract was acidified with hydrochloric acid when isocoumarin-3-acetic acid (0.25 g.) separated. It crystallised from acetic acid in cream coloured needles, m.p. 220° (Found : C, 64.5; H, 4.1. $C_{11}H_8O_4$ requires : C, 64.5; H, 3.9%).

IR Spectrum : Absorptions at 1740 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl) and 1710 cm^{-1} (acid carbonyl).

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